

Ethanobotanical Studies of Plants used by Flokllore of Vidisha District in the Treatment of Stone and Active Principal of Few Plants

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Abstract:- Medicinal plant have been known great demand in both developing countries in primary healthcare. Today a very large number of population suffering from the stones disease. Various traditional system of medicine together with homeopathy and folklore medicine continue to play a significant role largely in the health care system of the populations. Stone disease can be change our life style and food habits. The tribal and rural population of India are mostly dependent on medicinal plant. We know the Vidisha district are situated in central part of Madhya Pradesh. Peoples of this district go to healers use different kinds of herbs, minerals, animal parts and other material which are easily obtainable in that area. Medicinal plant used for removal of stone from the different body parts from thousands of years due to minor side effects. In this research 15 plant species are identified with 10 Angiospermic families are used. Amaranthaceae include 5 species, 2 species of Brassicaceae, rutaceae, euphobiaceae, nyctagenaceae, poaceae, malvaceae, solanaceae, fabaceae, apiaceae each. The present article described the potential of medicinal plants for stones dissolving properties.

Keywords:- Stone disease, Medicinal plant, Traditional healer, Madhya Pradesh.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since disease, decay and death have always co-existed with life the study of disease and their treatment must also have been contemporaneous with down of human intellect. The knowledge of medicinal plants must have been accumulated in the course of many centuries (Lt. Colonel K. R. Kirtikar, F.L.S., I.M.S., Volume-1 2000). Vidisha is a city and district in the central Indian state Madhya Pradesh, near its Bhopal. The forest covering geographical area is only 20% and 10% in shore district and Vidisha district respectively. Mostly in this district forest belt produced large population density of Dalbergia, Tectona, Terminalia species. This forest produce high efficiency of timber, fuel, bamboo and good yields. A traditional system requires Vidisha 23°20' and 24°22' North

latitudes and 77°16' and 70°18' East longitudes. Peoples of these district used to traditional healers for their primary health ailments along with modern health care center. The district harbours a variety of trees, shrubs, herbs, climber and grasses. The ethnobotanically important medicinal plants are found in Vidisha district. The tribal peoples are used their different part of plants for the treatment of many disease. (Hari Shankar Lal and Sanjay Singh, 2012, 3(1):91-96. Most of these ethnic communities do not have their own scripts and written language, the information about prescriptions, pharmacology, attitude toward disease, diagnosis etc; of the age old tribals medicine are lying unclaimed. The people belonging to modern society are not aware of this rich knowledge system.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

For our present research we carried out study of ethnobotanical evidence and selection of various plant material regular field tour is conducted in Vidisha district for March 2021 to continue. With the help of herbarium and floras. We identified the botanical name, local name, family name, habit, habitat and date and place of collection for different types of plant species used in kidney stone, gallbladder stone and urinary stone. Medicinal properties of the plants are learned through the expert and old knowledge of aged person in this village and tribals.

III. ENUMERATION

A number of group discussion will be also conducted in the properties of medicinal plants during the period of investigation. The present study of medicinal plants survey conducted in forest areas of Vidisha district resulted in established plant use of 15 plant species related to 10 angiospermic families comprising botanical name of species, family, common name, of species in tribal areas. This study will be used to show the analysis of secondary metabolites of plant origin and its effect on microbial pathogens, which will be quite useful to the phytochemical workers and pharmaceutical companies related to drugs of herbal medicines. We selected following species shown in the table:

S no	BOTANICAL NAME	FAMILY	COMMON NAME	PART USE	USES
1	<i>Aervalanata (L.)</i>	Amaranthaceae	Gorkhabundi, khali	Leaves	cough, sore throat, diabetes, lithiasis
2	<i>Beta vulgaris (L.)</i>	Amaranthaceae	Garden beet	Roots	1 glass of beet root juice taken early morning to dissolve urinary stone.
3	<i>Amarenthusviridis (L.)</i>	Amaranthaceae	Green Amaranth	All parts	Given in kidney stone.
4	<i>AmaranthusCaudatus (L.)</i>	Amaranthaceae	Love-lies-bleeding, Velvet flower	Leaves	Extract is give in kidney stone.
5	<i>Achyranthesaspera (L.)</i>	Amaranthaceae	Chaff-flower, Devil's horsewhip	Roots	Urolithiasis, urinary tract
6	<i>ArmoraciaLopathifolia</i>	Brassicaceae	Horse radish	Seeds	Diuretic, kidney stones
7	<i>Barbarea Vulgaris (L.)</i>	Brassicaceae	Yellow Rocket	Roots and Leaves	For kidney stone
8	<i>Cynodondactylon (L.)</i>	Poaceae	Dhoob, Durva grass	Whole plants with roots	Extract of whole plant with roots taken orally twice a day for 8-10 days to dissolve kidney stones.
9	<i>Bridolia Montana (L.)</i>	Eupobiaceae	Sugar beet	Rhizomes	Daily two glass of rhizomes of sugar beet juice is given for kidney stones
10	<i>AegleMarmelose (L.)</i>	Rutaceae	Wood apple, Beal	Leaves and Fruit	15 gram of Fruit pulp powder is taken with coconut milk for 15 days to Lithiasis.
11	<i>Borhaaviadiffusa (L.)</i>	Nyctagenaceae	Hogweed, punarnava	Roots	Roots decoction is given daily for one month in kidney stones
12	<i>Gossypumherbaceum (L.)</i>	Malvaceae	Arabian cotton, cottongen	Fruits	Unripe fruits roasted in burning ash after orally to taken for kidney stone
13	<i>Solanumvirginianum(L.)</i>	Solanaceae	Yellow -fruit night shade, Thai green egg plant	Roots	Roots powder is mixed with a curd and taken once a day for 5-7 days for dissolving kidney stones.
14	<i>Vignaunguiculata (L.)</i>	Fabaceae	Chavla	Seeds	100 ml decoction of seeds taken orally twice a day for 30 days
15	<i>Amnvisnaga (L.)</i>	Apiaceae	Khella	Whole plants	Urolithiasis, urinary tract

Table 1: LIST OF PLANTS DRUGS USED IN KIDENY STONE, GALL STONE, URINARY STONE

We find their usage in herbal formulation in treatment of kidney stone by native folklore of Vidisha district. Tribals and villagers living in the remote forest areas or it's vicinity.

IV. RESULT

A total of 15 plants species belonging to 10 Angiospermic families are related to ethno medicinal properties. Due to information Vidisha district indicates the tribal and other village people are good knowledge about herbal drugs. All over views the medicinal plant play a vital role in stone disease and the angiospermic plant are used in treatment of kidney stone, gallbladder stone and urinary stones. Over all the table 1 presenting whole plant species enumerating the scientific name, local name, family, part used and they effect on over body parts.

V. DISCUSSION

The undesirable effect of the modern medicine has already diverted the attention of the people towards herbal medicines. Hence, Traditional therapies can be used in primary health system. This health care system more expensive for all society of the peoples. All elder ethnic people are familiar with the different type of plant species can be used in various type of diseases. We can establish therapeutic properties of these preparation of safe use.

VI. CONCLUSION

The result of the present information gathered from Vidisha district signified that the tribals, and other peoples of in village most priority of the herbal medicinal plants of usages in kidney stone, gallbladder stones and urinary stones. Mostly vital ethno botanical plants are reported in this tribal areas. They can be used in traditional therapeutics treatment for safe purpose.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to the Vidisha district folk peoples and are thankful to the Dr. vandana sharma for sincere guidance and appreciation from time to time during the course of this investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1.] S. Phillips, Graeth R. Tudor, nephrocalcinosis and nephrolithiasis. Radiological imaging of kidney, Springer Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2011, Page No. 395-401.
- [2.] Rohit kumar Bijauliya, Shashi Alok, S.K. Jain, V.K. Singh, Devendra Singh, review international journal of pharmaceutical science 2017 herbal and allopathic medicine for kidney, gallbladder and urinary stones.
- [3.] Jadhev V.M. et al traditional medicinal uses of hibiscus rosasinensis journal of pharmacy research 2009, 1220-1222.
- [4.] Alkasawarkar, C.R. Jangde, P.D. Thakre, Ranu Kadoo and Sushma Shelu analgesic activity of hibiscus rosasinensis in rat veterinary world, 2009 vol. 2 (9) 352-354.
- [5.] Nidal AJ. Medical plants utilized in Palestinian folk medicine for treatment of diabetes mellitus and cardiac diseases. J Al-Aqsa Univ 2005;9;2005.
- [6.] Drury H. The useful plants of India. New Delhi; Research Press; 2010.
- [7.] Sharma N, Singh TB, Vijayvergia R. Study of medicinal plants in Aravali regions of Rajasthan for treatment of kidney stone and urinary tract troubles. Inst J PharmaTech Res 2022;3(1);110-113.
- [8.] Ghatapanadi SR, Johnson N, Rajasab AH. Medicinal plants of North Karnataka used in treatment of kidney stone and urinary tract infections. Socioscan 2010;2(4);23-24.
- [9.] Prachi N, Chauhan D, Kumar MS. Medicinal plants of muzaffarnagar district used in treatment of urinary tract and kidney stone; Indian J. Tradition Knowledge 2009;8(2):191-195.
- [10.] Morcos SK, Morcos S, Thomson H. Urogenital imaging. A problem – oriented approach. John Wiley Sons, UK. 2009; 196 – 199.
- [11.] Suman Kumar Mekap, Satyaranjan Mishra, Sabuj Sahoo, Prasana Kumar Panda. Antiuro lithiatic activity of Crataeva magna bark. Ind J Nat Prod and Resour. 2011; 1(2): 28 - 33.
- [12.] Surendra K Pareta, Kartik Chandra Patra, Ranjit Harwansh. In-vitro calcium oxalate crystallization inhibition by Achyranthes indica Hydroalcoholic extract: An approach to antilithiasis. Int J Pharma Bio Sci. 2011; 2(1): 432 - 437.
- [13.] Chopra RN, Nayar SL and Chopra IC, 1956. Glossary of Indian Medicinal plants council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, India.
- [14.] Chopra RN, Chopra IC and Verma BS, 1969. Supplement to the Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, India.
- [15.] Cooke T, 1958. The Flora of the Presidency of Bombay, Vols 1-3 Reprinted edition, Government of India, India.
- [16.] Devesh Kumar and Mishra PK, 2011. Plant based Contraceptive popular among tribals of Jarkhand, Bioscience Discovery, 2(1): 11-14.
- [17.] Hari Shankar Lal and Sanjay Singh, 2012. Study of Plant Biodiversity of Hazaribag District, Jharkhand India and its Medicinal Uses, Bioscience Discovery, 3(1): 91-96.
- [18.] Jain SK (ed.), 1989. Methods and approaches in Ethnobotany, Society of Ethnobotanists, Lucknow, India.
- [19.] Jain SK, 1991. Dictionary of Indian folk medicine and Ethnobotany, Deep publications, New Delhi, India.
- [20.] Jain SK, 1996. Ethnobiology in Human welfare, Deep publications, New Delhi, India.
- [21.] Jain SK, 1999. Dictionary of Ethnoveterinary Plants of India, Deep publications, New Delhi, India.
- [22.] Jain SK & Mudugal. 1999. A Handbook of Ethnobotany, Bhisensingh Mahendrapal Singh, Dehradun, India.
- [23.] Kapur LD, 2001. Handbook of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plants. CRC Press, London. Kirtikar KR & Basu BD, 1933. Indian Medicinal Plants, Vol. 1-4, Publisher L M Basu, Allahabad.
- [24.] Mohammad NI and Suradkar SS, 2011. Ethnobotanical and Ethnomedicinal study of some medicinal plants of Barshitalatahsil, District Akole (MS), India., Bioscience Discovery, 02 (2): 236-239.
- [25.] Prachi, Chauhan N, Kumar D and Kasana MS, 2009. Medicinal plants of Muzaffarnagar District used in treatment of urinary track and Kidney stone, Indian Journal of traditional Knowledge, 8 (2): 191-195.
- [26.] Patil JU and SD Biradar, 2011. Folkloric medicinal plants of Hingoli District, Maharashtra, Indian Journal of National Products and Resources. 2(1): 97-101.
- [27.] Pullaiah T and Ravi Prasad Rao B, 1995. Flora of Nizamabad, Andhra Pradesh India, Bhisensingh Mahendra palsingh, Dehradun, India.
- [28.] Reddy SC, Reddy KN, Thulsi Rao K and Chiranjibi Pattanaik, 2007. Ethnobotanical Studies on Medicinal plants used by the Chenchus of Nallamalais in Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh, India, Research Journal of Medicinal Plant, 1 (4) :128-133.
- [29.] Reddy SC, Gopal Krishna and Raju VS, 2008. Phytotherapy at Rural Communities: A Case Study from the Gonds of Wartangal District, Andhra Pradesh, India, Research Journal of Botany, 3(2): 97-102.

- [30.] Sharma PP and Singh NP. 2001.Ethnobotany of Dadra Nagar Haveli and Daman, (Union Territories), Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, India.
- [31.] Varsha S Rathod, 2011.Ethnopharmacognostical Studies of Thewtiaperwana (Pers.)K. Schum. A Potential psychoactive Plant, Bioscience Discovery,2(1):139-142.